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Sr-isotope analysis of speleothems by LA-MC-ICP-MS: high temporal resolution and fast data acquisition

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28 **Abstract**

29 Speleothems are well established climate archives. A wide array of geochemical proxies,
30 including stable isotopes and trace elements are present within speleothems to reconstruct past
31 climate variability. However, each proxy is influenced by multiple factors, often hampering
32 robust interpretation. Sr isotope ratios ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) can provide useful information about water
33 residence time and water mixing in the host rock, as they are not fractionated during calcite
34 precipitation. Laser ablation multi-collector-inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry
35 (LA-MC-ICP-MS) has rarely been used for determination of Sr isotope signatures in
36 speleothems, as speleothems often do not possess appropriately high concentrations of Sr to
37 facilitate this analysis. Yet the advantages of this approach include rapid data acquisition, higher
38 spatial resolution, larger sample throughput and the absence of chemical treatment prior to
39 analysis. We present LA-MC-ICP-MS Sr isotope data from two speleothems from Morocco
40 (Grotte de Piste) and India (Mawmluh Cave), and we compare linescan and spot analysis
41 ablation techniques along speleothem growth axes. The analytical uncertainty of our LA-MC-
42 ICP-MS Sr data is comparable to studies conducted on other carbonate materials. The results
43 of both ablation techniques are reproducible within analytical error, implying that this technique
44 yields robust results when applied to speleothems. In addition, several comparative
45 measurements of different carbonate reference materials (i.e. MACS-3, Jct-1, JCp-1), including
46 tests with standard bracketing and comparison of the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios with a nanosecond laser
47 ablation system and a state-of-the-art femtosecond laser ablation system, highlight the
48 robustness of the method.

49

50 **Keywords:** Speleothem; Strontium isotopes; Laser ablation, Multi-collector inductively
51 coupled plasma mass spectrometry, Femtosecond

52 **1. Introduction**

53 Speleothems (cave CaCO₃ deposits) are well established climate archives and are found
54 worldwide in karst environments (Asmerom et al., 2010; Cheng et al., 2016; Cruz et al., 2005;
55 Genty et al., 2003; Hoffmann et al., 2016; Kennett et al., 2012; Luetscher et al., 2015; Wang et
56 al., 2001). They can be dated with unprecedented precision using the ²³⁰Th/U-dating method
57 (Richards and Dorale, 2003; Scholz and Hoffmann, 2008), and provide a range of climate
58 proxies that record a number of environmental processes and can be analysed at up to sub-
59 annual resolution.

60 Oxygen isotopes in speleothems ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values) depend on paleo-temperature and rainfall
61 properties, such as amount, seasonality and moisture sources (e.g., Fairchild et al., 2006;
62 McDermott, 2004), whereas carbon isotopes can provide information on soil productivity,
63 vegetation characteristics and effective rainfall (McDermott, 2004). In addition, trace elements
64 (e.g., Sr, Mg, P, Ba) may be interpreted in terms of effective infiltration, prior calcite
65 precipitation, water residence time, source and reservoir effects, weathering processes in the
66 epikarst zone and soil composition (Ayalon et al., 1999; Fairchild et al., 2000; Fairchild and
67 Treble, 2009; Verheyden et al., 2000; Wassenburg et al., 2016a; Wassenburg et al., 2016b).
68 Within the epikarst and soil zone, different sources of trace elements (for example aeolian dust
69 vs. host rock) may be present and display varying compositions. A change in the dripwater
70 pathway or in the relative contribution of different sources, may thus affect the dripwater trace
71 element composition, which often renders their interpretation a challenging task (Banner et al.,
72 1994).

73 Important information on the influence of different sources of trace elements in dripwaters may
74 be provided by Sr isotopes, which have been shown to provide additional insights on
75 precipitation and water residence time in the host rock (Banner et al., 1996; Oster et al., 2010).
76 In CaCO₃, the Sr²⁺ ion substitutes at the Ca²⁺ ion sites in the mineral lattices due to their similar

77 properties and ionic radii (Banner, 2004). No isotopic fractionation of Sr isotopes is observed
78 during precipitation of CaCO₃ and the incorporation of Sr into the crystal lattice. Thus, the
79 ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr ratio of carbonates is identical to that of the parent solution (Banner and Kaufman,
80 1994).

81 Although the first Sr isotope analyses on speleothems were conducted in 1990 (Avigour et al.,
82 1990), relatively few studies have focused on this topic so far. The main source for Sr in
83 speleothems is the host rock, but several factors have been proposed to affect Sr isotope ratios:
84 varying water residence time in the epikarst (Banner et al., 1996); (Oster et al., 2010; Oster et
85 al., 2014; Verheyden et al., 2000), changes in aeolian input in response to sea-level changes or
86 atmospheric circulation (Goede et al. 1998; Ayalon et al. (1999); Bar-Matthews et al. (1999);
87 Li et al. (2005); Zhou et al. 2009), changes in weathering intensity of soil and host rock in
88 response to rainfall (Avigour et al., 1990), changes in the distance to the shoreline and
89 incorporation of sea-salt signals (Fisher et al., 2010), as well as mixing of the Sr signals of
90 different rock types and soils (Frumkin and Stein (2004); Hori et al. (2013)). All these studies
91 either used Thermal Ionization Mass Spectrometry (TIMS, Avigour et al. (1990); Goede et al.
92 (1998); Frumkin and Stein (2004); Li et al. (2005); Zhou et al. (2009); Hori et al. (2013)), or
93 solution MC-ICP-MS (multi-collector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry, Ayalon
94 et al. (1999); Bar-Matthews et al. (1999); Verheyden et al. (2000); Fisher et al. (2010); (Oster
95 et al., 2010; Oster et al., 2014). For both techniques samples need to be drilled/milled, and
96 require chemical separation prior to mass spectrometric analysis. This is time-consuming, and
97 limits the achievable spatial resolution of ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr records. Strontium isotope analysis by laser
98 ablation (LA-) MC-ICP-MS offers the opportunity to measure the ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr ratio *in-situ* at high
99 spatial resolution and without any prior chemical treatment. Although this technique has been
100 widely applied to petrological samples (e.g. Christensen et al. (1995); Davidson et al. (2001);
101 Waight et al. (2002); Bizzarro et al. (2003); Ramos et al. (2004); Jackson and Hart (2006), and

102 carbonate and phosphate materials, such as gastropods, otoliths, teeth, clam shells, fine- and
103 coarse-grained carbonates and corals (Christensen et al. (1995), Ehrlich et al., 2001, Outridge
104 et al. (2002), Bizzarro et al., 2003, Ramos et al., 2004, Woodhead et al. (2005), Copeland et al.
105 (2008), it has only recently been used for measuring $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ in speleothems (Wortham et al.,
106 2017).

107 Here we present a LA-MC-ICP-MS method for measuring Sr isotopes on speleothems, based
108 on previously mentioned studies on different sample materials. We show results from two
109 speleothem samples and compare different sampling techniques. Both samples consist of
110 aragonite and have a rather high Sr concentration $>300 \mu\text{g/g}$, which makes them highly suitable
111 to apply LA-MC-ICP-MS. We also discuss the effects of different tuning parameters and
112 compare results obtained by two different laser systems (a New Wave UP 213 nm laser and a
113 NWR Femto200 laser ablation system).

114

115 **2. Speleothem samples**

116 The investigated speleothem samples stem from two different caves. Stalagmite GP5 was
117 sampled at Grotte de Piste (Morocco), and stalagmite MAW-4 stems from Mawmluh Cave
118 (Meghalaya, India). Stalagmite GP5 has a total length of 78 cm. A detailed description of the
119 cave and the sample is given in Wassenburg et al. (2012) and Wassenburg et al. (2013). In this
120 study, an approximately 15 cm long part of the sample (Fig. 1) was studied which corresponds
121 to the time span from ca. 800 to 1760 AD. Previous data is published in Wassenburg et al.
122 (2013) and only briefly summarised here. GP5 was precisely dated by the $^{230}\text{Th}/\text{U}$ -method.
123 Furthermore, the mineralogy of the sample was investigated by XRD and showed that GP5 is
124 mainly aragonitic, with minor calcitic parts ($<2\%$). Strontium concentrations range from 200 to

125 500 $\mu\text{g/g}$, with an average concentration of 426 (± 49) $\mu\text{g/g}$. In some parts, the sample is
126 characterized by mm-scale layering of porous and less porous layers.

127 Stalagmite MAW-4 (Fig. 1) from Mawmluh cave is a small sample with a total length of 3 cm.
128 The upper part of the sample (~ 15 mm), consists of aragonite, and covers the time span from
129 1950 to 2006 AD (Wassenburg et al., 2016b). It has an average growth rate of ~ 293 $\mu\text{m/a}$, and
130 can thus provide very high resolution. The stalagmite was actively growing at the time of
131 collection (March 2006). The lower part of the sample consists of calcite, the base is dated 395
132 ± 55 a BP. The calcite-to-aragonite transition is clearly visible by a change in colour from
133 greyish (calcite) to white/beige (aragonite). In the upper aragonitic part, this stalagmite has a
134 relatively high Sr concentration (1458–1729 $\mu\text{g/g}$, (Wassenburg et al., 2016b), and is thus
135 extremely suitable for Sr isotope measurements by LA-MC-ICP-MS. The calcite section has a
136 Sr concentration of a few hundred $\mu\text{g/g}$, and was not investigated in this study. For more
137 information about the cave setting and microclimatic conditions, see Breitenbach et al. (2010)
138 and Breitenbach et al. (2015).

139

140 **Figure 1:** [A] Sampling approach for speleothem GP5. The red rectangle indicates the sampling
 141 section, blue lines show the LA-MC-ICP-MS linescan positions. The spot analyses were

142 performed near the right end of the third linescan as indicated by the blue spots. [B] Sampling
143 approach for speleothem MAW-4. The red rectangle indicates the sampling section. Linescan
144 and spot analyses are similarly indicated as in [A]. All line lengths, widths and distances are on
145 scale.

146

147 **3. Materials and methods**

148 **3.1 Analytical setups**

149 The measurement routine was developed with a NU Plasma MC-ICP-MS (see Table 1 for cup-
150 configuration) coupled with a New Wave UP213 nm Nd:YAG laser ablation system at the Max
151 Planck Institute for Chemistry, Mainz. Measurements were also performed with the MC-ICP-
152 MS coupled to a NWR Femto200 laser ablation system to compare results obtained with two
153 laser ablation systems. The femtosecond laser is less sensitive to matrix effects that may cause
154 isotope fractionation (Poitrasson et al., 2003; Vanhaecke et al., 2010). Prior to laser ablation,
155 the MC-ICP-MS was coupled to a CETAC Aridus II Desolvating Nebulizer system for tuning.
156 The Sr reference solution NIST SRM 987 was used for optimizing the peak shape and
157 coincidence of the individual Sr isotopes (^{88}Sr , ^{87}Sr , ^{86}Sr , ^{84}Sr) and to test the influence of
158 different tuning parameters on ion beam intensity and the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio. Several tuning
159 parameters were changed systematically. Tests showed that the gas flows of the Aridus
160 introduction system have a significant effect on the Sr isotope ratios. Furthermore, the torch
161 position and the tuning of the high voltage lenses are important, since they affect the sample
162 introduction into the system and the ion beam inside the mass spectrometer. Finally, the source
163 lenses have been shown to have a significant effect on the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio. In order to test the
164 effects of changes in the lens settings, we started with seven measurements of NIST SRM 987
165 to test the stability of the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio over time. In a first step, the lens settings were tuned

166 for maximum ^{88}Sr intensity. Subsequently, the different source and transfer lens settings were
 167 changed systematically. For each lens, three measurements were performed: First, the voltage
 168 of the lens was decreased by 10 V, then increased by 20 V, and finally decreased by 10 V to
 169 return to the original value. This procedure was performed for all seven source and transfer
 170 lenses. Results are presented in Fig. 2 and Supplement A1.

171
 172 **Figure 2:** $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios obtained on reference solution NIST SRM 987. The orange line
 173 represents the literature value of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.71034 \pm 0.00026$ (GeoReM, (Jochum et al., 2005),
 174 the shading in bright orange shows the 2σ standard error. The large fluctuations in the Sr isotope
 175 ratio are caused by changes in the settings of the source and transfer lenses of the NU Plasma
 176 MC-ICP-MS, marked by the black arrows. Black diamonds represent measurements with the
 177 original lens settings, while blue (red) diamonds represent measurements with a 10 V increase
 178 (decrease) in lens voltage in comparison to the original lens setting.

179

180 Settings were then further optimised with the NU MC-ICP-MS coupled to the LA system. Since
181 the UP213 nm laser ablation system offers higher fluence values (20 – 30 J/cm²) and count rates
182 than the femtosecond laser (0.7 – 0.8 J/cm²), this system allows measurement of samples with
183 comparably low Sr concentrations (>200 µg/g). Potential matrix effects are assessed by
184 comparison with the femtosecond laser. All samples and reference materials have a low Rb
185 content (Table 2). The operating parameters for the MC-ICP-MS and the laser ablation systems
186 are given in Table 3.

187

188 **3.2. Reference materials**

189 The reference material (RM) Jct-1 was measured to determine the accuracy and precision of
190 the method. This modern marine carbonate sample originates from a recent giant clam and has
191 a ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr-ratio comparable to modern sea water (⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr of 0.70918 ± 0.00001, 2σ, Faure and
192 Mensing (2005)), as confirmed by solution MC-ICP-MS measurements (⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr = 0.70915 ±
193 0.00005, Ohno and Hirata (2007)). Recently, a more precise ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr ratio of 0.70917 ± 0.00001
194 has been obtained for Jct-1 by MC-ICP-MS (Weber et al., In Revision). Due to its comparable
195 Sr content of 1400 µg/g (Aizawa, 2008), Jct-1 was chosen as RM for the measurements of
196 samples GP5 and MAW-4. Furthermore, the RMs JcP-1, a modern coral with ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr =
197 0.70916 ± 0.00002 (Ohno and Hirata (2007)) and MACS-3, a synthetic carbonate pellet
198 (⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr = 0.7075532 ± 0.0000037; Jochum et al. (2011)), were also tested. Both of these RM
199 samples have a very high Sr concentration (7500 µg/g for JcP-1, (Aizawa, 2008), and
200 6760 µg/g for MACS-3, (Jochum et al., 2012) and are well suited for femtosecond laser
201 analysis. For tuning and test measurements, we used a modern day bivalve shell of *Glycymeris*
202 sp., which has two distinct areas of different Sr concentrations of ca. 1000 and 5000 µg/g.

203

204 3.3. Laser ablation sampling method

205 Multiple LA-MC-ICP-MS measurements were performed perpendicular to the growth axis of
206 the speleothem samples, parallel to and within the same distinct growth layers to check for
207 reproducibility. In order to identify the best method for analysing Sr-isotope ratios in
208 speleothems by LA-MC-ICP-MS, we applied two different sampling methods. First, we used
209 the linescan technique, which has the advantage that a high signal intensity can be maintained
210 for a relatively long measurement interval, improving counting statistics. In contrast, for spot
211 analyses, the signal intensity slowly decreases with ablation depth. However, for spot analyses,
212 mixing of material from different growth layers is excluded. The linescans followed individual
213 growth bands and each of usually three linescans per growth layer had a circular spot size of 80
214 – 100 μm and a length of 750 μm (except linescan GP5-7, which was 2000 μm). They were
215 scanned with a scan-speed of 5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$, providing about 150 s per linescan measurement. This
216 sampling approach enables us to identify potential changes in the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio at a very high
217 spatial resolution. Prior to each analysis, a pre-ablation was performed with a spot size of
218 110 μm and a scan-speed of 80 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ (Table 3). The first 5 s are discarded due to high intensities
219 when the laser starts, which is typical for laser ablation analyses. Spots were analysed with a
220 circular spot size of 100 μm and a dwell time of 120 s. To test the reproducibility of the method,
221 three line scans were placed parallel to each other within the same growth band with less than
222 50 μm between the end and start of each linescan (Fig. 1). The distance between the measured
223 layers varied between 150 μm and 850 μm for GP5 and 500 μm for MAW-4. The spot analyses
224 of GP5 were performed for a few layers only. Each spot analysis is located near the end of the
225 respective line scan. For correction purposes, RM JcT-1 was measured three times before and
226 after each set of samples (usually six measurements in total).

227 To compare both laser ablation systems, we performed measurements with different RMs.
228 Since the Sr concentration of JcP-1 is almost six times that of JcT-1, the laser settings for the

229 UP213 laser ablation system were adjusted to prevent the ^{88}Sr intensity from reaching critical
230 values. We used a laser energy of 60 %, a repetition rate of 5 Hz and a spot size of 55 μm . All
231 measurements were performed as spot analyses. To test the robustness of the results, we also
232 applied our standard bracketing approach on JCp-1 by measuring samples of JcT-1 before and
233 after JCp-1. The laser settings for JcT-1 were chosen as described in Table 3.

234 Our NWR Femto200 laser ablation system only allows spot sizes up to 65 μm , therefore we
235 only measured RMs with high Sr concentrations, such as JCp-1 and MACS-3. The laser
236 parameters for these measurements are presented in Table 3. Spot measurements with the
237 femtosecond laser ablation system suffer from a rapid decrease in signal intensity. Thus, all
238 measurements were performed as linescans. We measured three samples of JCp-1, followed by
239 six measurements of MACS-3 and again three samples of JCp-1.

240

241 **4. Correction procedure for LA-MC-ICP-MS**

242 Strontium isotopes were measured on cups H4 (^{88}Sr), H2 (^{87}Sr), Ax (^{86}Sr) and L3 (^{84}Sr)
243 (Table 1). The major advantage of Sr-isotope analysis with LA-MC-ICP-MS is that Sr-isotopes
244 are measured *in-situ*, without the need of chemical separation. This means, however, that the
245 matrix contains several other isotopes that potentially affect the Sr isotope signal (i.e., ^{87}Rb , but
246 also doubly charged ions, such as ^{176}Yb , ^{174}Yb , ^{172}Yb , ^{168}Yb , ^{168}Er , and molecular interferences,
247 such as Ca-argides and/or -dimers, Table 1). In addition, the Ar gas may contain impurities of
248 Kr, with interfering isotopes of ^{86}Kr and ^{84}Kr (Table 1). Some masses are affected by several
249 interferences. For example, the ^{84}Sr signal on mass 84 may be affected by $^{84}\text{Kr}^+$, $^{168}\text{Er}^{2+}$ $^{168}\text{Yb}^{2+}$
250 and Ca argides/dimers. Therefore, it is necessary to find another mass that is not affected by
251 other interferences, which can be used to correct for other masses of the same ion using known
252 isotopic abundances. For example, we used mass number 86.5 that is mostly unaffected by other

253 signals to correct for the Yb-interference by monitoring $^{173}\text{Yb}^{2+}$. Thus, the order of the
254 corrections is important. The correction procedure is outlined in detail below. Fig. 3 shows the
255 magnitude of the individual correction steps on the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio for measurements on samples
256 JcT, GP5 and MAW-4.

257

258 **4.1 Background correction**

259 Potential interferences of ^{86}Kr , ^{84}Kr , ^{83}Kr and ^{82}Kr from minor contaminations in the Ar gas
260 supply are corrected by a blank measurement. For this reason, prior to each analysis an on-peak
261 background correction is performed for 45 s during the laser warm-up time. Then, the median
262 for each signal intensity is calculated and subtracted from the measured signal. This removes
263 all Kr interferences as well as potential remains of Sr from previous measurements.

264

265 **4.2 Rare-earth elements (REE)**

266 After background correction, different interferences must be eliminated. Doubly-charged
267 isotopes of Er and Yb can be detected on half masses (Table 1). ^{173}Yb is the only isotope
268 measured on cup H1 on half-mass 87.5, and ^{171}Yb is the only one measured on cup L1 on half
269 mass 85.5. Thus, ^{173}Yb and ^{171}Yb can be measured without any interferences. By assuming
270 constant isotope ratios for Yb (Berglund and Wieser (2011)), the signal for all Yb isotopes can
271 be calculated. Although Yb is quite rare in speleothem samples (Table 2), this correction may
272 have a minor influence on the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios.

273 The second step is to correct for Er. ^{167}Er is the only isotope measured on ion counter IC-1 on
274 half mass 83.5, and other Er isotopes can be calculated assuming constant isotope ratios in the
275 same way as Yb (Berglund and Wieser (2011)). Erbium is uncommon in speleothem samples
276 (Table 2) and this correction is only of minor importance. Several laser ablation studies on other

277 sample materials did not even correct for rare earth elements (REE) during Sr isotope analysis
278 (e.g. Christensen et al. (1995); Barnett-Johnson et al. (2005); Jochum et al. (2009); Copeland et
279 al. (2010)).

280

281 **4.3 Molecular interferences**

282 The next step is to correct for molecular interferences of Ca dimers and argides. Since it is
283 impossible to differentiate between the signals resulting from argides and dimers, the relative
284 amounts of each signal are taken into account to correct for those interferences in relation to
285 the signal on mass 82. This mass is used as a reference since it has **no** other interferences and a
286 potentially higher signal of argides and dimers than mass 83, which is also free of significant
287 interferences (Table 1). As an example, we briefly describe the correction of mass 84 for Ca
288 argides and dimers.

289 After correcting for background and REEs, the correction for Ca argides is performed by the
290 following relationship:

$$291 \quad 84_{ArCorr} = 84_{uncorr} - 82_{uncorr} * \left(\frac{\sum CaAr_{84}}{\sum CaAr_{82}} \right) \text{(Eq. 1)}$$

292 where 84_{ArCorr} is the corrected signal on mass 84, 84_{uncorr} is the uncorrected signal (besides
293 background and REE correction) on mass 84 and 82_{uncorr} is the signal on mass 82. $\sum CaAr_{84}$ is
294 the sum of the relative portion of Ca argides on mass 84, and $\sum CaAr_{82}$ is the sum of the relative
295 portion of Ca argides on mass 82, based on their natural occurrence (Berglund and Wieser,
296 2011). This correction is performed for masses 88, 86, 84 and 83. For the interferences from
297 Ca dimers, the correction is done in a similar way, again using the signal on mass 82 as a
298 reference:

$$299 \quad 84_{Corr} = 84_{ArCorr} - 82_{uncorr} * \left(\frac{\sum CaCa_{84}}{\sum CaCa_{82}} \right) \quad \text{(Eq. 2)}$$

300 where 84_{corr} is the corrected signal on mass 84, 84_{Arccorr} is the background corrected intensity on
 301 mass 84, REEs and Ca argides, and 82_{uncorr} is the uncorrected signal (besides background and
 302 REE correction) on mass 82. ΣCaCa_{84} is the sum of the relative portion of Ca dimers on mass
 303 84 and ΣCaCa_{82} is the sum of the relative portion of Ca dimers on mass 82. This correction is
 304 performed for masses 88, 87, 86, 85, 84 and 83 and only applied for signals > 0 V. All other
 305 signals remain uncorrected because the intensity of Ca argides and dimers is too small to detect
 306 and does not affect the results.

307

308 **4.4 Mass bias**

309 After correcting the raw signals for interferences, the mass bias needs to be corrected. This
 310 correction is performed prior to the correction for the interference of Rb, because the mass bias
 311 obtained from the $^{86}\text{Sr}/^{88}\text{Sr}$ ratio is subsequently used to obtain the mass bias corrected
 312 $^{85}\text{Rb}/^{87}\text{Rb}$ ratio (section 4.5). Based on the signals corrected for background, REEs, Ca argides
 313 and dimers, raw values for the ratios of $^{86}\text{Sr}/^{88}\text{Sr}$, $^{84}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ and $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ are calculated. Then, a
 314 mass fractionation factor α is calculated to correct for the instrumental mass fractionation based
 315 on the $^{86}\text{Sr}/^{88}\text{Sr}$ ratio and the exponential law described in Ingle et al. (2003):

$$316 \quad R_{\text{corr}} = R_{\text{meas}} * \left(m_{87\text{Sr}} / m_{86\text{Sr}} \right)^\alpha \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

317 where m_{87} and m_{86} are the masses of ^{87}Sr and ^{86}Sr . The mass fractionation factor α is calculated
 318 as described in Ehrlich et al. (2001):

$$319 \quad \alpha = \left(\ln \left(\frac{\left(\frac{^{86}\text{Sr}}{^{88}\text{Sr}} \right)_{\text{true}}}{\left(\frac{^{86}\text{Sr}}{^{88}\text{Sr}} \right)_{\text{meas}}} \right) \right) / \ln(m_{86} / m_{88}) \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

320 where $(^{86}\text{Sr}/^{88}\text{Sr})_{\text{true}}$ is the accepted value of 0.1194 (Steiger and Jäger, 1977) and m_{88} is the
 321 mass of ^{88}Sr .

322

323 **4.5 Interference of rubidium**

324 The final step in the correction procedure is to correct the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio for the interference of
325 ^{87}Rb . Due to the previous corrections, mass 85 only consists of ^{85}Rb (Table 1), which can be
326 used to calculate the fraction of ^{87}Rb by using the constant ratio of $^{87}\text{Rb}/^{85}\text{Rb} = 0.3857$
327 (Berglund and Wieser (2011) This was done following equation 5:

$$328 \quad {}^{87}\text{Rb} = \left(\frac{{}^{87}\text{Rb}}{{}^{85}\text{Rb}_{\text{Lit}}} * {}^{85}\text{Rb}_{\text{meas}} \right) * \left(\frac{m_{87}}{m_{85}} \right)^\alpha \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

329 where $^{87}\text{Rb}/^{85}\text{Rb}_{\text{Lit}}$ is the literature value (Berglund and Wieser, 2011)(Berglund and Wieser,
330 2011)(Berglund and Wieser, 2011), $^{85}\text{Rb}_{\text{meas}}$ is the Rb signal on mass 85, corrected for
331 background, REEs and Ca argides/dimers, m_{87} is the mass of ^{87}Rb , m_{85} is the mass of ^{85}Rb , and
332 α is the mass fractionation factor. The correction on $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ is then performed using the
333 following equation:

$$334 \quad \frac{{}^{87}\text{Sr}}{{}^{86}\text{Sr}_{\text{RbCorr}}} = \left[\frac{({}^{87}\text{Sr}_{\text{uncorr}} - {}^{87}\text{Rb})}{{}^{86}\text{Sr}} \right] * \left(\frac{m_{87}}{m_{86}} \right)^\alpha \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

335 where $^{87}\text{Sr}_{\text{uncorr}}$ is the Sr signal on mass 87 corrected for background, REEs and argides/dimers
336 (not for Rb), ^{87}Rb and ^{86}Sr are the corrected signals for Rb on mass 87 and Sr on mass 86,
337 respectively, m_{87} and m_{86} are the masses for Sr and α is the mass fractionation factor. This Rb
338 correction is only considered robust for samples with a Rb/Sr ratio <0.02 (Irrgeher et al., 2016).
339 For samples with higher Rb content, an alternative Rb-correction is necessary (Müller and
340 Anczkiewicz, 2016). All speleothem samples and RMs analysed in this study are below this
341 threshold (Table 2).

342

343 **4.6 Data processing**

344 After calculating the interference-free $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio, the results are calibrated by standard-
 345 bracketing using RMs with well-known $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios, as has been recommended for Sr-
 346 isotope analysis (Irrgeher et al., 2016). Furthermore, to avoid effects of individual large peak
 347 values, we performed a 2σ outlier test for the median of all $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ values, removing all values
 348 deviating $>2\sigma$ from the median.

349 Usually, the final $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios obtained for the RMs deviate slightly from the reference
 350 values, necessitating an additional correction step. Each sample is therefore bracketed by a set
 351 of three individual measurements of a suitable RM. The mean value of the three RMs is
 352 calculated, and a correction factor for the sample is calculated according to the following
 353 equation:

$$354 \quad Sr_{Corr} = \frac{{}^{87}\text{Sr}/{}^{86}\text{Sr}_{true}}{{}^{87}\text{Sr}/{}^{86}\text{Sr}_{meas}} \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

355 where $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}_{true}$ is the literature value of the RM and $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}_{meas}$ is the measured ratio of the
 356 RM. We then use the mean value of the two correction factors from the two sets of RMs
 357 (measured prior and subsequent to the sample) and apply it to the measured sample $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$
 358 ratio. Since the measurements of the RMs are associated with an uncertainty, error propagation
 359 is performed by adding the relative 2σ standard error for the measurement of the RM (2σ Std
 360 Err_{Ref}) to the relative 2σ standard error of the measured sample (2σ Std Err_{Spl}):

$$361 \quad 2\sigma \text{ Std Err}_{SampleCorr}[\%] = \sqrt{(2\sigma \text{ Std Err}_{Ref}[\%])^2 + (2\sigma \text{ Std Err}_{Spl}[\%])^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

362 The 2σ Std Err_{Ref} value is calculated from the mean of the relative 2σ standard errors of all
 363 RMs, while the 2σ Std Err_{Spl} is calculated from the mean of the linescans or spot measurements
 364 for each sample layer. By applying the error propagation, the 2σ standard error of each sample
 365 usually increases by $\pm 0.00001 - 0.00002$ (0.01 – 0.03 ‰).

366

367 **5. Results**

368 The results from the speleothem samples obtained with the two sampling methods (linescans
369 and spot analyses, respectively) are presented in Table 2. Due to the extensive correction
370 procedure, we show the effect of each correction step on the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ value for one LA-MC-
371 ICP-MS measurement of JcT-1, MAW-4 and GP5, respectively. The results are presented in
372 Fig. 3. The correction step associated with the largest effect is the background correction and,
373 depending on the sample, the corrections for interferences of Yb and Rb. Corrections for Ca
374 argides and dimers are insignificant for our results.

375

376 **Figure 3:** Influence of the different correction steps on the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio of JcT-1 (black
377 diamonds), MAW-4 (squares) and GP5 (triangles). Note that all results are mass bias corrected.

378

379 **5.1. Influence of tuning parameters on the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio**

380 Our solution MC-ICP-MS measurements show that tuning for maximum Sr intensity does not
381 necessarily lead to a “true” $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio, but may deviate from the accepted value of the
382 reference solution NIST SRM 987 ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.71034 \pm 0.00026$, GeoReM, Jochum et al.
383 (2005)) on the third or fourth decimal. This can be avoided by tuning the mass spectrometer to
384 obtain the Sr isotope ratio known from the literature (at the expense of signal intensity). The
385 procedure is described in chapter 3.1. While some changes have a large influence on the isotope
386 ratio (e.g. the decrease by 10 V for source lenses V1 and V2), others only have a minor
387 influence, such as the changes at transfer lens H1 (Fig. 2). We note that this might be a specific
388 pattern for our mass spectrometer and may differ in other laboratories. After restoring to the
389 original setting, the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio was comparable to the starting value (Fig. 2).

390 Figure 4 (data in Supplement A1) shows the evolution of the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio during consecutive
391 days of LA-MC-ICP-MS measurements of RM Jct-1. While the Sr isotope ratio increased
392 during the first measurements, source lens adjustments brought the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio back towards
393 the reference value.

394

395 **Figure 4:** $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios of reference material Jct-1 obtained during different days, showing
 396 the tuning influence during the first measurements. The orange line represents the reference
 397 value of Jct-1 of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.70917 \pm 0.00001$ (Weber et al., In Revision), the shading in bright
 398 orange corresponds to its 2σ standard error. Dashed vertical lines separate different days of
 399 measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is
 400 referred to the web version of this article.)

401

402 These results highlight the necessity of the standard-bracketing approach, which corrects the
 403 described effects. Nevertheless, we minimised the influence of these effects by tuning the
 404 $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio towards the reference value prior to the measurement, or, if necessary, again
 405 afterwards.

406

407 5.2 Tests with reference materials

408 5.2.1 Nanosecond LA-MC-ICP-MS

409 For the nanosecond laser ablation system, we chose the carbonate RMs JcT-1, JcP-1 and
410 MACS-3 and applied the method described above (section 3.3). These RM's have a large range
411 of Sr concentrations, and we are aware that changes of the laser parameters between different
412 samples can affect the measurements. Nevertheless, all measurements showed sufficient
413 fluence ($\sim 10 \text{ J/cm}^2$ for JcP-1 and MACS-3 and $> 22 \text{ J/cm}^2$ for JcT-1) and the obtained $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$
414 ratios showed the expected results within error. The mean value of the JcP-1 measurements
415 was $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.70913 \pm 0.00008$ ($n = 3$) and agree with the literature value of $0.70916 \pm$
416 0.00002 (Ohno and Hirata, 2007). In addition, the uncorrected JcP-1 $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio is 0.70914
417 ± 0.00007 ($n = 3$) and the uncorrected $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio of JcT-1 is 0.70917 ± 0.00005 ($n = 5$), thus
418 both are indistinguishable from the literature values. The results for MACS-3 provide an
419 average $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ value of 0.70753 ± 0.00005 ($n = 16$), which is in agreement with the literature
420 value of 0.7075532 ± 0.0000037 (Jochum et al., 2011).

421

422 5.2.2 Femtosecond LA-MC-ICP-MS

423 In order to further test our methodology, we used a femtosecond laser ablation system on
424 carbonate RM's with high Sr concentrations (JcP-1 and MACS3) following the method as
425 described in chapter 3.3. All measurements were corrected by the standard bracketing approach
426 yielding $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios in agreement with the reference values (Fig. 5). An exception is
427 measurement MACS-3-8, which shows a strongly elevated $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio. This sample may
428 have been affected by changes in the Kr signal intensity because unusual peak intensities in
429 ^{84}Kr were observed during the blank measurement. It is thus likely that similar fluctuations
430 occurred during the measurement which affected the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio. The measured raw $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$
431 ratios before the standard bracketing correction for JcP-1 are 0.70920 ± 0.00004 ($n = 6$) and
432 0.70757 ± 0.00005 for MACS-3 (without MACS3-8, $n = 5$), in agreement with the literature
433 values. After performing the standard bracketing approach, the average $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio is

434 0.70917 ± 0.00006 for JCp-1 (n = 6) and 0.70752 ± 0.00006 for MACS-3 (without MACS3-8,
 435 n = 5).

436

437 **Figure 5:** $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios of reference materials JCp-1 and MACS-3 obtained by fs-LA-MC-
 438 ICP-MS. The red line represents the literature value of MACS-3 of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.7075532 \pm$
 439 0.0000037 (Jochum et al., 2011), the blue line shows the literature value of JCp-1 of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$
 440 $= 0.70916 \pm 0.00002$ (Ohno and Hirata, 2007), with its 2σ standard error shown as bright blue
 441 shading. The error range for the reference value of MACS-3 is too small to be visible in the
 442 figure. Note that sample MACS-3-8 was strongly affected by very variable ^{84}Kr intensities
 443 during the blank measurement and probably during the sample measurement as well.

444

445 5.3 Speleothem GP5

446 On sample GP5, a total number of 27 different layers were measured (Fig. 6 [A]). In the area
 447 between ~ 116 to 118.5 mm distance from top (DFT) the resolution is high (i.e. less than $100 \mu\text{m}$
 448 between linescans). Further measurements were performed with a distance of $\sim 1000 \mu\text{m}$

449 between each other. Some measurements suffer from changing mass bias and low intensities
450 ($^{88}\text{Sr} < 1 \text{ V}$), resulting in decreasing values of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ (in particular linescans GP5-17-21,
451 Table 2). The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios generally show only minor variations, ranging from $0.70856 \pm$
452 0.00017 to 0.70920 ± 0.00007 . The low-resolution measurements from 108.3 to 115.3 mm DFT
453 show a relatively stable Sr isotope composition with $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios between 0.70890 ± 0.00011
454 and 0.70913 ± 0.00008 . The average $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio of all linescans is 0.70892 ± 0.00006 ($n =$
455 79).

456 36 spot analyses were performed on stalagmite GP5. These were placed near the right end of
457 the third linescan within the same growth layer (Fig. 1). At signal intensities lower than ca.
458 0.6 V on ^{88}Sr , we found a significant decrease of the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio. Corresponding
459 measurements are marked with double diamonds $\blacklozenge\blacklozenge$ in Table 2. The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios of the spot
460 measurements from GP5 are presented as circles in Fig. 6 [A]. The results show a similar pattern
461 as the linescans, even though the 2σ standard errors are slightly larger. The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio varies
462 between 0.70872 ± 0.00024 and 0.70907 ± 0.00011 . The mean of all spot measurements is
463 $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.70897 \pm 0.00005$ ($n = 32$) and in good agreement with the linescan data.

464

465 **5.4 Speleothem MAW-4**

466 On MAW-4, 24 linescans were performed at a sampling resolution of 500 μm (Fig. 1). The
467 $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios are presented in Fig. 6 [B]. While the first two measurements at 8.4 and 8.9 mm
468 DFT are similar, the following measurements show a slightly increasing trend towards higher
469 values, reaching a maximum of 0.70871 ± 0.00004 . The 2σ standard error of all measurements
470 is ± 0.00004 with an average $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio over all linescans of 0.70867 ± 0.00003 ($n = 24$).

471 24 spot analyses were performed on stalagmite MAW-4, placed near the right end of the third
472 linescan within the same growth layer (Fig. 1). Note that layer MAW-4-7 was not measured.

473 For layer MAW-4-8, a total number of six spot measurements were performed to test the
474 reproducibility. The mean of MAW-4-Spot-8a-c is within error of the mean of MAW-4-Spot-
475 8d-f. Since MAW-4-Spot-8a-f are in perfect agreement, they were combined as a single
476 measurement (MAW-4-Spot-8). The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios of the spot measurements of MAW-4 are
477 presented as circles in Fig. 6 [B]. A pattern, similar to the linescans can be observed with two
478 measurements at 8.4 and 8.9 mm DFT showing lower $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios compared to the other
479 values. In contrast to the linescan measurements, this increase is not significant due to larger
480 errors. Nevertheless, an increase and a plateau at the same distance from top is visible for the
481 spot analyses. The 2σ standard error of all measurements is in the range of ± 0.00006 to
482 ± 0.00008 and therefore higher than for the linescans. The average $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio over all spot
483 measurements is 0.70870 ± 0.00002 ($n = 24$), in agreement with the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio derived from
484 the linescans.

485

486 **Figure 6:** [A] $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios are plotted against the distance from top of speleothem GP5.
 487 Linescan measurements affected by low signal intensities are marked red. [B] $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios
 488 of speleothem MAW-4 against distance from top [mm] for the linescan as well as the spot
 489 analyses. For better visualization of the error bars, spot analyses data were shifted to the right
 490 by 0.05 mm.

491

492 6. Discussion

493 6.1 Linescan versus spot analysis

494 We used two different laser ablation methods for this study, i.e., linescans along growth bands
495 and spots, to test which is the best approach. In general, the linescan method provides much
496 smaller 2σ standard errors than the spot analysis. For RM JCt-1, the final $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio usually
497 has a 2σ standard error in the range of $\pm 0.00002 - 0.00005$ for linescan measurements,
498 representing a total error in the range of $0.003 - 0.01\%$. For spot analyses, the 2σ standard error
499 was in the range of $\pm 0.00005 - 0.00007$. The 2σ standard error is highly dependent on the Sr
500 concentration of the sample (Fig. 7). The different precision in spot and linescan analyses is
501 caused by: 1) the longer integration time for the linescan approach, and 2) decreasing signal
502 intensity during spot analysis caused by deepening of the laser crater. Therefore, the spot
503 analysis approach might be insufficiently precise to resolve small scale changes in the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$
504 ratio. This is exemplified in MAW-4, where an increase in the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio was significant
505 for the linescan approach, but not for the spot analyses due to larger errors. A disadvantage of
506 the linescan approach, however, is that unwanted sampling of material from different growth
507 layers (with a different $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio) may occur. Furthermore, linescans require a larger
508 sample surface compared to spot analysis. We recommend using the linescan approach only for
509 speleothems with a regular (parallel) layering that provides a relatively large sample surface
510 (ca. 3 mm width and length). For speleothems with irregular layering, spot analysis may be the
511 preferable option. Tests with spot analyses showed that higher repetition rates (> 10 Hz) result
512 in a higher signal intensity and precision, which is desirable for samples with relatively low Sr
513 concentration (200-500 $\mu\text{g/g}$), such as GP5. However, the sample material should be dense and
514 stable enough to resist such a high ablation efficiency. Higher repetition rates also result in
515 deeper laser craters and thus potentially in ablating into different layers. However, for repetition
516 rates in the range of $5 - 10$ Hz the depth of the crater should be $\leq 12\ \mu\text{m}$ and even less for
517 linescan measurements ($\leq 2\ \mu\text{m}$). Thus, this effect should only be important for very slowly
518 growing speleothems.

519
 520 **Figure 7:** Scatter plot of ^{88}Sr intensity vs. $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ 2σ standard error. The dependency of the
 521 $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ 2σ standard error on the ^{88}Sr intensity is shown for the linescan measurements of Jct-
 522 1, *Glycimeris* sp., GP5 and MAW-4.

523
 524 **6.2 Nanosecond versus femtosecond laser systems**

525 Ablating RMs JcP-1 and MACS-3 with either a nanosecond or a femtosecond laser gives
 526 similar results. While the nanosecond laser provides the advantage of measuring lower
 527 concentration samples with higher precision, the femtosecond laser is less vulnerable to
 528 fractionation effects and offers better control on the ablation process (Glaus et al., 2010; Koch
 529 and Gunther, 2007). In addition, the refractory Sr is generally less affected by matrix, elemental
 530 and isotopic fractionation effects in comparison to the volatile Rb (Horn and von Blanckenburg,
 531 2007). However, with our setup, the femtosecond laser approach requires much higher Sr

532 concentrations ($> 1400 \mu\text{g/g}$) to achieve sufficient precision. For instance, we were not able to
533 accurately measure JCt-1 and our speleothem samples with the femtosecond laser due to
534 insufficient Sr concentration. In contrast, the standard bracketing approach with JCt-1 and JCp-
535 1 with the nanosecond laser was successful and the data from MACS-3 were similar to literature
536 values. The results from the femtosecond LA-MC-ICP-MS measurements show that our
537 approach can be transferred to other laser ablation systems. The raw measurements of JCp-1
538 and MACS-3 are in good agreement with literature values and the performance of our standard
539 bracketing approach does not affect the resulting $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ significantly. Overall, the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$
540 RM data obtained with both laser ablation systems agree within error and are therefore probably
541 not affected by differences in matrix effects between the different setups.

542

543 **6.3. Tuning parameters and suitable reference materials**

544 An aspect of major importance identified during the development of the LA-MC-ICP-MS
545 technique is to adjust the tuning after changing the cones to obtain correct $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios of a
546 reference solution. Tuning for maximum signal intensity does not always result in the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$
547 ratio of the RM (Fig. 2). To achieve the correct $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio we adjusted the lens settings. In
548 comparison to the tuning of the high voltage lenses, the source and transfer lenses had a larger
549 effect on stability and reliability of the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios with our NU Plasma MC-ICP-MS
550 (Fig. 2). In addition, the laser ablation system itself alters the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios of the
551 measurements. Since different RMs and samples have variable Sr contents, the laser energy and
552 spot size may have to be adjusted to prevent signal intensities larger than ~ 10 V on cup H4 (^{88}Sr
553 signal). It is important to use similar measurement parameters for RMs and speleothem samples
554 when the standard bracketing technique is applied. Therefore, it is essential to use a RM with
555 similar Sr concentration and a similar matrix as the speleothem sample. By not using matrix-
556 matched samples and RMs, potential differences in the occurrence of interference may alter the

557 correction (Irrgeher et al., 2016). In case of different matrices and/or large differences in Sr
558 concentration, the resulting $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio of the unknown sample needs to be handled with care
559 and might be less precise. For instance, the use of RM Jct-1 for correcting GP5 measurements
560 was critical, due to low intensities on the sample (1 – 2 V, ^{88}Sr) and high intensities on the RM
561 (up to 8 – 9 V, ^{88}Sr) when using the same laser parameters. Fluence decreases with laser energy
562 and it is not guaranteed that the same measurement parameters are available for all samples and
563 RMs. For speleothem samples with much higher Sr concentration than in this study, JcP-1 and
564 MACS-3 are suitable RMs.

565 Furthermore, the signal intensity of the Sr isotope measurements is important. Measurements
566 suffering from very low intensities on ^{88}Sr ($\sim < 1$ V) show large errors. A scatter plot of the
567 intensity of the ^{88}Sr -signal against the 2σ standard error for the linescan measurements of Jct-
568 1, the bivalve shell of *Glycimeris* sp., GP5 and MAW-4 (Fig. 7) reveals in particular for GP5 a
569 high dependency on a sufficiently high Sr signal for precise measurements. Intensities of ^{88}Sr
570 below ~ 1.5 V cause a dramatic shift towards large errors. Similar patterns are visible for Jct-1
571 and the *Glycimeris* sp. shell. The Sr intensity difference found in MAW-4 is too low to show
572 the effect of signal intensity on the uncertainty. All measurements with low Sr intensities suffer
573 from low counting statistics and the background correction of Kr might be insufficient.

574 Another effect that can have major detrimental influence on the analysis is progressive clogging
575 of the cones. When a decrease in Sr intensity is observed, it is important to evaluate if this
576 change results from a change of the Sr content in the sample or from clogging of the cones by
577 deposition of Ca. Additional information on the performance of the mass spectrometer is
578 provided by monitoring the mass bias. In our study, the mass bias for the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ -ratio was
579 usually between 0.45 – 2.09 % ($R_{\text{corr}}/R_{\text{meas}} = 0.9791 - 0.9955$, Eq. 3). Especially for the
580 linescans of sample MAW-4, the mass bias remained very stable (1.24 – 1.27 %; $R_{\text{corr}}/R_{\text{meas}} =$
581 0.9873 – 0.9877, Eq. 3). When the mass bias shows increased variability over the day, careful

582 evaluation of the results is necessary. We observed that a decrease in the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio and an
583 increase in the 2σ standard error is often related to a high mass bias (e.g., for samples GP5-17-
584 21, Table 2).

585

586 **6.4 Standard bracketing**

587 Our results highlight the importance of the standard bracketing correction scheme for LA-MC-
588 ICP-MS Sr isotope analysis. Prior to the first sample measurements, a test of the standard
589 bracketing method was performed using Jct-1. For this purpose, Jct-1 was used as a RM and
590 also treated as a sample. The raw and corrected results are shown in Fig. 8. The standard
591 bracketing method seems to be generally applicable for $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio correction, since the
592 corrected Sr isotope ratios of Jct-1 agree within uncertainties. A similar test performed on the
593 RMs JcP-1 and MACS-3 with the femtosecond LA-MC-ICP-MS setup also showed reliable
594 results (Fig. 5).

595

596 **Figure 8:** Black rhombs show the raw results of the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ LA-MC-ICP-MS linescan
597 measurements performed using Jct-1 as a reference material and a sample. Corrected $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$

598 ratios of Jct-1 are shown as red rhombs. Note that the errors increased in comparison to the raw
599 data due to correction via the reference material. The orange line represents the reference value
600 of Jct-1 of 0.70917 ± 0.00001 (Weber et al., In Revision).

601

602 **6.5 LA-MC-ICP-MS of Sr isotopes on speleothem samples**

603 Traditional Sr isotopes analysis by solution MC-ICP-MS or TIMS requires careful chemical
604 treatment. A recent study by Wortham et al. (2017) presented a speleothem Sr isotope record
605 obtained by LA-MC-ICP-MS. These authors performed linescan measurements parallel to the
606 growth axis of a speleothem from Brazil and traced an increasing $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio over the last
607 two millennia. Their approach is slightly different to ours. While their linescan is performed
608 parallel to the growth axis, we measure three linescans for each growth layer perpendicular to
609 the growth axis, which enables us to test whether results from individual growth layers are
610 reproducible (similar to the Hendy test for stable carbon and oxygen isotopes, Hendy (1971)).
611 In addition, the change of the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio in the Brazilian speleothem was on the third
612 decimal, which is relatively large. Detecting smaller changes (i.e., on the fourth to fifth
613 decimal), is only possible by conducting a set of measurements perpendicular to the growth
614 axis. Otherwise the obtained $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio is largely influenced by a time-averaging effect.
615 Wortham et al. (2017) used a different sampling approach and do not provide the Sr
616 concentration of their speleothem and the used RM which complicates the comparison of both
617 studies. Nevertheless, they showed that it is possible to track large changes in speleothem Sr
618 isotope ratios using linescans parallel to the growth axis. Our results show that it is also possible
619 to obtain higher precision Sr isotope data by LA-MC-ICP-MS using a set of linescans, as well
620 as spot analyses orientated perpendicular to the growth axis. With the state-of-the-art MC-ICP-
621 MS systems, it is unlikely that small scale changes in Sr isotope composition can be detected
622 by performing a linescan parallel to the growth axis. This is further complicated by the typically

623 low Sr concentration of speleothems (few hundred $\mu\text{g/g}$ or even less). However, aragonitic
624 speleothems can have much higher Sr concentrations of several thousand $\mu\text{g/g}$. Thus, in
625 aragonitic samples, a linescan parallel to the growth axis may reveal small-scale changes in Sr
626 isotope composition.

627

628 **7. Conclusions**

629 We show that LA-MC-ICP-MS is a powerful tool for the analysis of Sr isotopes in speleothems.
630 Best results are obtained from samples with Sr concentrations of $>1000 \mu\text{g/g}$. For our setup, the
631 minimum ^{88}Sr concentration required to obtain reliable $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios was ca. $300 \mu\text{g/g}$. In
632 order to retrieve reliable results, appropriate tuning of both the mass spectrometer and the laser
633 ablation system is of great importance. Tuning for maximum intensity does not always result
634 in correct $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios. We highly recommend to tune for the correct Sr-isotope ratio of a
635 reference material prior to an analytical session. The Sr concentration of the RM should be in
636 the same range as that in the samples. In order to account for potential drifts in the mass
637 spectrometer during an analytical session, we recommend to apply standard bracketing using
638 appropriate RMs.

639 Linescans provide higher precision than spot analyses. The latter might be advantageous
640 however if only a limited surface is available for sampling, for instance in case of a irregular
641 layering. While speleothem samples tested here contain only low amounts of REEs and Rb,
642 appropriate correction procedures are required to minimise the influence of interferences from
643 these elements. In addition, potential interferences resulting from Ca argides and dimers should
644 be accounted for.

645 The use of a femtosecond laser ablation system provides a more stable signal intensity and
646 therefore more precise measurements, but its application on samples with low Sr concentrations

647 (ca. >1400 $\mu\text{g/g}$, since measurements with Jct-1 were not precise enough) is not recommended
648 due to lower signal intensities compared to the nanosecond laser leading to less precise results.

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862 climate and environment. *Chemical Geology*, 268(3–4): 233-247.

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864

865 **Table 1:** NU Plasma collector block assignments used for *in-situ* LA-MC-ICP-MS Sr isotope analysis of speleothems. Collectors H1, H2, H4, Ax
 866 and L1 – L5 are Faraday cups, IC-1 is an ion counter.

867

Collector	H4	H2	H1	Ax	L1	L2	L3	IC-1	L4	L5
Single Mass	88	87	86.5	86	85.5	85	<u>84</u>	83.5	83	82
Double Mass	176	174	173	172	171	170	168	167	166	164
Isotope of interest	⁸⁸ Sr _{82.58%}	⁸⁷ Sr _{7.00%}	-	⁸⁶ Sr _{9.86%}	-	-	⁸⁴ Sr _{0.56%}	-	-	-
Singly-charged interferences	-	⁸⁷ Rb _{27.83%}	-	⁸⁶ Kr _{17.28%}	-	⁸⁵ Rb _{72.17%}	⁸⁴ Kr _{56.99%}	-	⁸³ Kr _{11.50%}	⁸² Kr _{11.59%}
Doubly-charged interferences	¹⁷⁶ Yb _{12.99%}	¹⁷⁴ Yb _{32.03%}	¹⁷³ Yb _{16.10%}	¹⁷² Yb _{21.68%}	¹⁷¹ Yb _{14.09%}	¹⁷⁰ Yb _{2.98%}	¹⁶⁸ Yb _{0.12%}	-	-	-
Molecular interferences	-	-	-	-	-	¹⁷⁰ Er _{14.91%}	¹⁶⁸ Er _{26.98%}	¹⁶⁷ Er _{22.87%}	¹⁶⁶ Er _{33.50%}	¹⁶⁴ Er _{1.60%}
Molecular interferences	⁴⁰ Ca ⁴⁸ Ca	⁴⁴ Ca ⁴³ Ca	-	⁴⁰ Ca ⁴⁶ Ca	-	⁴² Ca ⁴³ Ca	⁴⁰ Ca ⁴⁴ Ca	-	⁴⁰ Ca ⁴³ Ca	⁴⁰ Ca ⁴² Ca
Molecular interferences	⁴⁰ Ar ⁴⁸ Ca	-	-	⁴⁰ Ar ⁴⁶ Ca	-	-	⁴⁰ Ar ⁴⁴ Ca	-	⁴⁰ Ar ⁴³ Ca	⁴⁰ Ar ⁴² Ca

868

869 Note that only collectors used during analysis are shown in this table. Potential interferences affecting the Sr masses are also illustrated along with
 870 natural abundances for Sr, Rb, Kr, Yb and Er (Berglund and Wieser (2011)). Abundances for molecular interferences of Ca dimers and argides are not

871 shown for reasons of clarity. Some masses have a large number of potential interferences of Ca argides and dimers (e.g. mass 86 with $^{43}\text{Ca}^{43}\text{Ca}$,
872 $^{40}\text{Ca}^{46}\text{Ca}$, $^{42}\text{Ca}^{44}\text{Ca}$, $^{48}\text{Ca}^{38}\text{Ar}$, $^{46}\text{Ca}^{40}\text{Ar}$). Here, only the two most common molecular interferences are shown. Prior to each analysis, the peak center
873 was determined on mass 84 (L3) using the signal of ^{84}Kr in the gas flow of Ar. Therefore, mass 84 is underlined.

874 **Table 2:** Results of the linescan analysis from speleothem samples GP5 and MAW-4. The
875 alignment of the different cups is presented with the corresponding signal intensities. For most
876 sample layers, three runs were performed. For these samples, the mean of all runs is shown.

877

878 ♦ Sr-concentrations for sample GP5 were taken from Wassenburg et al. (2013) and Sr-
879 concentrations for sample MAW-4 were taken from Wassenburg et al. (2016b).

880 ♦♦ Not all of the three measurements from each spot were taken into account due to shifts in
881 the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio of measurements with low Sr-intensities (approximately below 0.7 V for
882 ^{88}Sr).

Sample	Distance from top [mm]	\bar{x} \diamond Sr conc [$\mu\text{g/g}$]	\bar{x} Total Sr [V]	\bar{x} Total Rb [mV]	\bar{x} Rb/Sr $\times 10^{-3}$	\bar{x} Er/Sr $\times 10^{-6}$	\bar{x} Yb/Sr $\times 10^{-6}$	\bar{x} $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	\bar{x} 2 σ Std Err	\bar{x} Mass Bias $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	Sample	Distance from top [mm]	\bar{x} Total Sr [V]	\bar{x} Total Rb [mV]	\bar{x} Rb/Sr $\times 10^{-3}$	\bar{x} Er/Sr $\times 10^{-6}$	\bar{x} Yb/Sr $\times 10^{-6}$	\bar{x} $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	\bar{x} 2 σ Std Err	\bar{x} Mass Bias $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	
<i>Linescans</i>											<i>Spotscans</i>										
<i>GP5</i>																					
GP5-1	118.4	344	0.9	0.08	0.09	1.3	703	0.70872	0.00013	1.23%	GP5-Spot-2	118.2	1.4	0.12	0.08	3.4	529	0.70906	0.00013	1.18%	
GP5-2	118.2	349	1.4	0.08	0.06	1.3	257	0.70893	0.00009	1.22%											
GP5-3	118.0	354	1.2	0.12	0.10	1.0	419	0.70886	0.00011	1.22%											
GP5-4	117.7	310	1.1	0.08	0.07	1.0	~ 0	0.70879	0.00011	1.21%											
GP5-5	117.5	292	1.2	0.10	0.09	1.0	1136	0.70875	0.00013	1.20%											
GP5-6	117.2	354	1.1	0.10	0.09	1.1	664	0.70891	0.00013	1.20%											
GP5-7	117.3	328	1.3	0.06	0.04	1.3	~ 0	0.70883	0.00006	1.18%											
GP5-8	118.1	357	2.1	0.12	0.05	1.2	363	0.70895	0.00007	1.02%											
GP5-9	117.8	335	2.0	0.13	0.06	1.2	497	0.70906	0.00007	1.05%											
GP5-10	117.1	343	1.5	0.19	0.13	1.0	121	0.70898	0.00009	1.14%	GP5-Spot-10	117.1	1.0	0.10	0.09	3.5	865	0.70901	0.00015	1.12%	
GP5-11	116.9	321	1.6	0.12	0.07	0.9	424	0.70900	0.00008	1.31%											
GP5-12	116.8	348	1.9	0.16	0.08	1.0	349	0.70893	0.00007	1.05%	GP5-Spot-12	116.8	1.4	0.11	0.08	2.7	919	0.70895	0.00014	1.95%	
GP5-13	116.6	338	1.9	0.15	0.08	1.1	289	0.70896	0.00007	1.07%											
GP5-14	116.5	340	1.8	0.11	0.06	1.0	268	0.70920	0.00007	1.38%	GP5-Spot-14	116.5	1.7	0.13	0.08	2.7	327	0.70904	0.00011	1.92%	
GP5-15	116.3	336	1.8	0.13	0.07	1.0	803	0.70902	0.00008	1.61%											
GP5-16	115.3	385	1.2	0.20	0.17	1.0	405	0.70890	0.00011	1.75%	GP5-Spot-16	115.3	1.6	0.08	0.05	2.7	487	0.70907	0.00011	1.93%	
GP5-17	114.3	416	1.1	0.10	0.10	1.0	501	0.70895	0.00011	2.03%	GP5-Spot-17♦♦	114.3	1.1	0.08	0.08	2.6	1116	0.70897	0.00011	1.87%	
GP5-18	113.3	353	0.9	0.14	0.16	1.1	441	0.70878	0.00014	2.09%											
GP5-19	112.3	363	0.8	0.17	0.22	1.1	179	0.70896	0.00014	1.82%											
GP5-20	111.3	381	0.7	0.16	0.22	0.9	136	0.70868	0.00015	1.87%											
GP5-21	110.3	427	0.7	0.13	0.19	1.1	285	0.70856	0.00017	2.23%	GP5-Spot-21	110.3	1.1	0.08	0.07	3.5	867	0.70895	0.00014	1.94%	
GP5-22	113.1	351	1.4	0.26	0.18	1.4	435	0.70898	0.00009	1.19%	GP5-Spot-22	113.1	1.2	0.07	0.06	2.9	757	0.70903	0.00013	1.91%	
GP5-23	112.1	425	1.5	0.19	0.13	1.6	~ 0	0.70913	0.00008	1.18%											
GP5-24	111.1	384	1.4	0.16	0.12	1.6	91	0.70909	0.00009	1.16%	GP5-Spot-24♦♦	111.1	0.9	0.11	0.12	3.0	763	0.70901	0.00014	1.93%	
GP5-25	110.1	497	1.3	0.16	0.12	1.5	~ 0	0.70907	0.00009	1.16%	GP5-Spot-25	110.1	1.3	0.08	0.06	2.9	244	0.70892	0.00013	1.96%	
GP5-26	109.3	412	1.3	0.20	0.16	1.7	~ 0	0.70905	0.00010	1.16%	GP5-Spot-26♦♦	109.3	1.1	0.12	0.12	3.3	564	0.70894	0.00014	1.98%	
GP5-27	108.3	373	1.4	0.23	0.17	1.6	233	0.70893	0.00009	1.16%	GP5-Spot-27♦♦	108.3	0.5	0.06	0.12	2.8	708	0.70872	0.00024	2.00%	
<i>Linescans</i>											<i>Spotscans</i>										
<i>MAW4</i>																					
MAW4-1	8.4	1729	4.8	0.06	0.01	0.4	1181	0.70862	0.00004	1.24%	MAW4-Spot-1	8.4	4.1	0.15	0.04	1.3	432	0.70867	0.00007	0.92%	
MAW4-2	8.9	1629	5.7	0.03	0.01	0.4	2295	0.70861	0.00004	1.25%	MAW4-Spot-2	8.9	3.6	0.08	0.02	1.2	694	0.70866	0.00007	0.97%	
MAW4-3	9.4	1526	4.8	0.04	0.01	0.5	623	0.70867	0.00004	1.25%	MAW4-Spot-3	9.4	4.2	0.09	0.02	1.3	1155	0.70870	0.00008	0.95%	
MAW4-4	9.9	1585	5.0	0.04	0.01	0.4	925	0.70870	0.00004	1.25%	MAW4-Spot-4	9.9	3.9	0.07	0.02	1.4	1011	0.70873	0.00008	0.88%	
MAW4-5	10.4	1600	4.9	0.06	0.01	0.4	1421	0.70870	0.00004	1.26%	MAW4-Spot-5	10.4	4.3	0.08	0.02	1.3	654	0.70874	0.00007	0.45%	
MAW4-6	10.9	1560	4.5	0.06	0.01	0.4	149	0.70871	0.00004	1.26%	MAW4-Spot-6	10.9	4.2	0.05	0.01	1.3	1116	0.70874	0.00007	0.49%	
MAW4-7	11.4	1595	4.7	0.12	0.02	0.4	552	0.70870	0.00004	1.27%											
MAW4-8	11.9	1458	4.2	0.07	0.02	0.5	624	0.70869	0.00004	1.27%	MAW4-Spot-8	11.9	5.6	0.10	0.02	0.8	609	0.70867	0.00006	1.99%	

884 **Table 3:** Operating parameters of the NU Plasma MC-ICP-MS and the two laser ablation
 885 systems.

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NU Plasma MC-ICP-MS

RF Power	1300 W
Argon cooling gas flow rate	13 L/min
Auxiliary gas flow rate	0.93 L/min
Interface cones	Ni
Lens settings	Optimized for maximum signal intensity and $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio
Mass resolution	Low
Mass analyzer pressure	$3\text{-}5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar
Detection system	Nine Faraday collectors and one Ion Counter
Sampling mode	Time Resolved Analysis

**New Wave UP213 nm
Laser ablation system**

**NWR Femto 200
Laser ablation system**

	Linescan	Spot	Linescan
Sampling approach	Linescan	Spot	Linescan
Wavelength	213 nm	213 nm	200 nm
Line length	750 μm		750 μm
Ar flow rate	0.65-0.79 L/min	0.68-0.78 L/min	0.77 L/min
He flow rate	0.65-0.81 L/min	0.68-0.78 L/min	0.77 L/min
<i>Pre-Ablation</i>			
Frequency	10 Hz	10 Hz	5 Hz
Translation rate	80 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$		60 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$
Beam width	100-110 μm	110 μm	65 μm
<i>Ablation</i>			
Frequency	10 Hz	5-10 Hz	25 Hz
Translation rate	5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$		5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$
Beam width	80-100 μm	100 μm	55 μm
Dwell time		120 s	
Fluence	20-30 J/cm ²	20-30 J/cm ²	0.7-0.8 J/cm ²
<i>Data Collection</i>			
Gas background	45 s	45 s	45 s
Sample	145 s	85-115 s	145 s
Integration	0.2 s	0.2 s	0.2 s

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